

DESIGN KNOCKDOWN FACTORS FOR COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO SPECTRUM LOADING BASED ON A RESIDUAL STRENGTH MODEL

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SUMMARY

Knockdown factors for static strength are calculated that incorporate changes in the distribution of residual strengths that occur during the lifetime of composites subjected to fatigue loading conditions.

Keywords: fatigue, knockdown factors, reliability-based design, residual strength, naval applications

INTRODUCTION

A critical need for increased use of composite materials is improved lifetime prediction methodologies to support more aggressive designs. Within the scope of this specific effort, we will investigate the impact of loading sequence and random spectrum loading on material properties. The goal is to provide statistical, experimental background for the development of knockdown factors/partial safety factors for composite design. In doing so, we will build on our previous approach implemented to estimate knock down factors by including durability simulations within a reliability-based framework, as shown in Figure 1. Through this process, we will examine the nature of mechanical degradation of the composite material and propose a design methodology for determining the material reduction factors to be used in probability-based design.

The long-term goal is to combine the understanding of environmental effects, fatigue and fatigue spectrum in a unified model to predict material behavior under realistic design conditions. We suggest that the use of such understandings could be reduced to a series of knock down factors, k_i , or partial safety factors that could be used in an allowable strength design approach as suggested here, where the applied stresses have to be smaller than the reduced strength.

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{app} &\leq \sigma_{ult} \prod_i k_i \\ &\leq \sigma_{ult} (k_{fatigue} k_{statistical} k_{moisture} k_{temperature} k_{aging} k_{UV} k_{weathering} k_{scale-up} \dots)\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

Obviously, including each of these effects is a daunting task in the analysis, and an even more daunting task in the required experimental characterization. For the purpose of this study, we have chosen to examine the first two effects so that we can define the appropriate static knockdown factor so that

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{app} &\leq \sigma_{ult} (k_{fatigue} k_{statistical}) \\ &\leq \sigma_{ult} \phi\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

where ϕ is the knockdown factor that corresponds to a particular specified probability of failure.

Figure 1. Design considering durability within a reliability based approach.

In this study, we use a residual strength-based fatigue model [1] to predict the fatigue lifetimes of composites subjected to spectrum loading conditions typical of naval ship applications. The approach is validated by comparisons with experimental data. In addition, because the model predicts the distribution of fatigue lifetimes, we are able to suggest appropriate knockdown factors on the static strength that provide a specified reliability.

APPROACH AND RESULTS

Sample Fabrication

One of the challenges associated with this design knockdown philosophy is developing sufficient data to support validation of the approaches used (given the expected scatter in fatigue properties). Indeed, one of the primary goals of this effort was to develop a database of properties that could be used to support future model development and validation. Composites used in this study were manufactured at Virginia Tech using Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM). The fiber reinforcement was Vetrotex 324 woven roving E-glass which has a 5:4 bias in the warp direction and the layup (denoted by warp direction in each layer) was $[0/+45/90/-45/0]_s$. Following a 24 hour cure period under ambient conditions, the material was post-cured for 4 hr. at 82°C . The material was manufactured in a series of batches under identical procedure, each producing a 0.9 m by 0.9 m panel 0.613 cm thick that was then cut into specimens,

having dimensions of 2.540 +/- 0.002 cm wide and 15.2 cm long. Additional details are available in Reference [2].

Quasi-Static and Constant Amplitude Fatigue Characterization

Quasi-static properties were determined from 30 tension and 30 compression tests. Subsequently, 184 constant amplitude fatigue tests were conducted at three R-ratios (0.1, -1, 10) with the applied stress normalized by the tension ($R=0.1$) or compression ($R=-1, 10$) median initial strength (Figure 1).

Fatigue failure lifetime data was collected for 184 specimens under three R-ratios, 0.1 (tension-tension), -1 (fully reversed tension-compression) and 10 (compression-compression). A power law S-N model was fit to the normalized fatigue life data:

$$\log(N) = A \log(Fa) + B \quad (3)$$

where

$$Fa = \sigma_{peak} / X_{t,c} \quad (4)$$

using the tensile strength, X_t , for $R=0.1$ and the compression strength, X_c , for $R=-1$ and $R=10$ to normalize the applied peak stress, and Fa is the estimated failure criterion value. The power law parameters, A and B , for the S-N curve at each R-ratio are calculated using linear regression on logarithmically transformed data using the value of the peak fatigue stress divided by the median initial strength as the independent variable. The median tensile strength of 348 MPa was used for $R=0.1$ and the median compression strength of 302 MPa was used for $R=-1$ and $R=10$ fatigue because it is believed that compressive failure dominates the fatigue life in both cases. The resulting parameters are reported in Table 1. For $R=0.1$ and $R=10$ a single power law curve fits the data well; however, for the fully reversed loading case, the fit was not so good due to an apparent change in the fatigue slope at an applied loading of about 35% of the ultimate strength. Thus, an alternate bi-linear model for this data with two sets of parameters is also presented. The intersection of these curves occurs at a normalized applied stress of $Fa=0.358$. When the applied stress is above this value, the low cycle parameters are used to calculate N and when the applied stress is below this intersection point, the high cycle parameters are used. Figure 5 shows the experimental fatigue data and curve fits.

Table 1: S-N and residual strength curve fit parameters based on least square regression analysis

	A	B	R ²
R=0.1 single curve	-6.88	1.548	0.953
R=-1 single curve	-8.34	0.152	0.927
R=-1 bilinear $Fa > 0.354$	-5.18	1.283	0.927
R=-1 bilinear $Fa < 0.354$	-11.15	-1.408	0.909
R=10 single curve	-14.40	0.500	0.875

Figure 2. Fatigue lifetimes as a function of normalized stress level.

The $R=0.1$ data provide the best fit with the least scatter in the data (largest R^2 value) while the $R=10$ S-N curve is particularly flat (inverse slope of 14.4) and has a corresponding greater degree of scatter. Since A and B are fit using least squares about the scatter in fatigue life for the data normalized to the median (50th percentile) initial strength, an implicit assumption is equal rank between the initial strength and the fatigue life of a given specimen. Although R^2 values are similar for a single or a bilinear curve for $R=-1$ values visually, the bilinear curve follows the data trend better, especially for higher stresses.

Subsequently, an extensive series of 303 residual strength tests under constant amplitude fatigue were performed by stopping the fatigue process at specified number of cycles and breaking the specimen in the dominant failure mode, tension for $R=0.1$ and compression for $R=-1$ and $R=10$. Residual strength data were collected for 3 fatigue stress levels at each R -ratio. The specimens are fatigued until the desired target lifetime and then broken in the dominant failure mode (tension for $R=0.1$, compression for $R=-1$, 10). When calculating the Weibull residual strength distribution from the experimental data, premature failures were included in ranking the residual strength results for tests performed at given stress level and number of cycles. This treats the premature failures as suspended tests that did not produce a result but are known to have a residual strength less than the specimens which survived the fatigue portion of the tests. While these data points cannot be used because the specimens failed at different (shorter) lives than desired, the actual residual strength results will be ranked correctly. This ranking procedure is demonstrated in Figure 3 and the example Weibull parameter calculation is shown in Table 2. The percent premature failures are taken to be the cumulative probability of the highest ranked premature failure. By following this

procedure, biasing the residual strength distribution calculated by only including the specimens that survived the fatigue is avoided.

Figure 3. Example of ranking residual strength data with premature failures

Table 2. Example Weibull Calculation for data shown in Figure 3.

Rank	$\ln(RS)$	$\ln(\ln(1/(1-Pf)))$
1		
2		
3	3.282	-1.308
4	3.291	-0.935
5	3.494	-0.632
6	3.513	-0.367
7	3.604	-0.121
8	3.641	0.118
9	3.643	0.365
10	3.646	0.643
11	3.790	1.026
Slope		4.3
Intercept		-15.3
α		4.3
β (MPa)		246
Weibull fraction premature fail		0.16

Table 3-

Table 5 provide the Weibull statistical results for each set of residual strength measurements in terms of applied stress and cycles.

Table 3. Compression residual strength results for constant amplitude R=-1 fatigue

Extreme stress applied (MPa)	Cycles applied	# of RS data points	# of pre-mature failures	α	β (MPa)	Weibull p (pre-mature)
-96.5	1298	10	0	11.8	324	0
-96.5	3894	11	0	16.5	294	0
-96.5	6491	4	5	4.9	247	0.55
-96.5	9087	7	3	5.7	256	0.28
-86.2	5481	10	0	17.7	292	0
-86.2	38364	7	4	12.3	254	0.35
-68.9	55635	10	0	7.7	294	0
-68.9	166904	10	0	9.5	292	0
-68.9	278174	9	1	5.8	270	0.07

Table 4. Tension residual strength results for constant amplitude R=0.1 fatigue

Extreme stress applied (MPa)	Cycles applied	# of RS data points	# of pre-mature failures	α	β (MPa)	Weibull p (pre-mature)
152	727	11	0	18	338	0
152	868	5	0	18.3	318	0
152	2180	11	0	14.6	317	0
152	3633	9	1	9.8	274	0.07
152	5086	10	0	7.7	273	0
114	7250	12	0	3.1	337	0
114	50751	5	5	1.9	168	0.49
82.7	90304	10	0	12.1	304	0
82.7	270911	9	1	3.8	248	0.07
82.7	451519	9	2	4.3	246	0.16
82.7	632127	4	3	3.9	194	0.41

Table 5. Compression residual strength for constant amplitude R=10 fatigue

Extreme stress applied (MPa)	Cycles applied	# of RS data points	# of pre-mature failures	α	β (MPa)	Weibull p (pre-mature)
-165	1620	10	0	22.3	332	0
-165	4860	9	1	9	294	0.07
-165	8100	5	5	8.5	272	0.49
-165	11339	0	6	N/A	N/A	0
-152	10313	11	0	13.5	303	0

-152	72184	0	6	N/A	N/A	0
-141	22551	10	0	16	303	0
-141	67652	5	5	3.7	259	0.49
-141	112753	8	2	7.8	265	0.18
-141	157854	1	7	N/A	N/A	0.88

Variable Amplitude Fatigue

The next in the development of the residual strength-based knockdowns is to verify that the residual strength model can predict changes in residual strength for non-constant amplitude loading conditions (in addition to the constant amplitude conditions for which it has been calibrated). Three 5000 cycle Rayleigh distributed load histories with target autocorrelations of 0.95, 0.5 and 0 respectively, based on the absolute value of successive extrema, were generated using the method described in Sarkani et al. [3]. A fourth distribution was created by sorting all of the extrema in the 0.95 autocorrelated spectrum from smallest to largest and placing alternating points at the beginning and end of the spectrum to achieve a highly correlated spectrum where the stress amplitude increased monotonically to 2500 cycles and then decreased monotonically in a symmetric way. The resulting spectrum has an autocorrelation of 0.99999. These four spectra are referred to as “Rayleigh0.0,” “Rayleigh0.5,” “Rayleigh0.95,” and “Rayleigh1.0.”

The residual strength life prediction method was then applied to each of these Rayleigh-distributed spectra. Failures were predicted when the instantaneous value of the residual strength was equal to the instantaneous loading peak value. Examples for the Rayleigh0.95 case are shown in Figure 4 for three different scaled stress levels.

Figure 4. Measured and predicted lifetimes for Rayleigh0.95 case.

Our ability to predict this spectrum result does provide confidence in our ability to use the residual strength analysis for design purposes. However, there are some caveats. There is no discernible difference in the fatigue lives of the specimens as a function of autocorrelation for the type of loading chosen, and non-residual strength based models (such as Miner’s rule) produce very similar predictions.

Knockdown Factor Calculation

Our ultimate goal is to be able to provide knockdown factor estimates based on our residual strength lifetime prediction scheme. To examine a reasonable realistic condition, a representative 30-year history spectrum, was created by NSWC-CD [4]. In this spectrum, a 5-year load spectrum is followed by 25 repetitions of a 1-year load spectrum (so that the load levels in the 5-year spectrum are greater in magnitude than those in the 1-year spectrum). To calculate a design knockdown factor, we assume that the initial strength distribution for the composite may be represented by a two parameter Weibull distribution so that

$$P_f = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\sigma}{\beta} \right)^\alpha \right] \quad (5)$$

For a given specified (desired) probability of failure, we can solve for the initial compression strength at this specified probability of failure

$$X_{P_f} = \beta \left[\ln \left(\frac{1}{1 - P_f} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \quad (6)$$

where we note that α and β may determined with a required confidence level based upon the available experimental data. (For the E-glass/vinyl ester composite studied here, the values of α and β are 26.2 and 305 MPa, respectively.) At a probability of failure of 10%, corresponds to a value of 280 MPa for X_{P_f} . The residual strengths are then calculated as

$$\frac{\sigma_r}{X_{P_f}} = 1 - \left[\int \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_a}{X_{P_f}} \right)^{\frac{1}{j}} \frac{dn}{N} \right]^j \quad (7)$$

where σ_a is the applied stress in each block of loading, and N is determined from Equation (3) with

$$Fa = \frac{\sigma_a}{X_{P_f}} \quad (8)$$

The scaled values of the stresses in the spectrum are then adjusted so that the composite is predicted to just survive. This scaling factor is then a function of: (1) the spectrum itself, (2) the properties of the composite, and (3) the allowed probability of failure. For the particular values studied here, the corresponding scaling (knockdown factor) is that the maximum stress is allowed to be 73% of the median compression strength for a probability of failure of 10%.

CONCLUSIONS

An extensive set of characterization data for E-glass/vinyl ester composites subjected to constant amplitude and spectrum loading conditions has been developed. To illustrate the utility of the knockdown analysis approach, static strength knockdown factors were computed for a loading histogram typical of naval ships. In the analysis, a calculated 5-year loading spectrum was applied, followed by twenty-five 1-year loading spectrum.

The analysis results suggest a static strength knockdown of 0.73 is appropriate for a probability of failure of 10%.

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